

TWO-WAREHOUSE INVENTORY MODEL FOR DETERIORATING ITEMS WITH EXPONENTIAL DEMAND RATE UNDER TWO LEVEL TRADE CREDIT AND SHORTAGES

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Abstract

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In the context of inventory management, many factors such as demand, trade credit, nature of the item, capacity of the warehouse and shortages makes the models more applicable. However, their integration in a single unified model is tractable. In this study, two-warehouse inventory model for deteriorating items is developed with exponential demand rate. The trade credit is adopted at both upstream and downstream simultaneously. Shortage is allowed and fully backlogged. The deterioration rate of the item is assumed time varying. The cost functions of the model were derived, and their convexity established. Based on the result, the total cost of maintaining the inventory is minimum when trade credit period expires before the total depletion of goods in the rented warehouse, indicating that it is more cost-effective for the retailer to order large quantity while taking smaller trade credit period. Result of sensitivity analysis reveals that the holding cost, warehouse capacity and the length of upstream trade credit period significantly influence the replenishment cycle and total cost.

Keywords: Backlogging; Exponential demand; Trade credit; Convexity and capacity constrained warehouse.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Inventory policies for deteriorating items are process and procedures used to manage inventory of items that have a limited shelf life or are subject to deterioration over time. Some factors such as originality and/or quality of item, proximity of warehouse to the customers, trade credit and good price tend to inspire demand exponentially. As a result, demand exceeding supply is inevitable which leads to shortages even though ordering large quantities of items may overcome the situation. However, the interplay between deterioration, exponential demand, trade credit and shortages in a capacity constrained

environment has not been addressed in the literature, but this is the realistic market situation. In this paper, all these realistic factors are simultaneously integrated in the developed inventory policy.

Most of the works in the literature only incorporated some not all of these (capacity of the warehouse, proximity of the warehouse to the customers, quality of the item in stocked, good price, and trade credit) realistic factors in developing inventory policies due to their interplay complexity. For instance, Mahato and Mahata (2021) developed a model in which the item does not only deteriorate continuously but that they expire with time. Such items are known as

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maximum lifetime. The demand considered is dynamic and trade credit is given at both upstream and downstream. Mukunda et al. (2022) developed a decision for products that exhibits deterioration and having expiration date considering pollution-based supply chain model in fuzzy environments. In that paper, they consider a two-echelon sustainable supply chain model with a single-vendor and a single-buyer by taking note of the detrimental impacts of environmental pollution due to production. Haruna Aliyu and Adamu (2025) developed two-warehouse inventory model when the items have expiry dates, and the demand is assumed constant.

In studies, such as Liang and Zhou (2011) considered constant demand when trade credit is adopted at the two levels to developed two-warehouse inventory model for deteriorating items where shortages are not allowed. Likewise, Aliyu and Sani (2021), developed the two-warehouse inventory model with the goal of investigating the impact of credit riskiness of retailer. Malumfashi et al. (2023) developed an Economic Production Quantity (EPQ) model where the demand is assumed time varying, shortages not allowed with the trade credit only at downstream level. The warehouse is single and assume to have unlimited capacity. Aliyu (2025) developed the two-warehouse inventory model with random dispatching policy for deteriorating items. The trade credit is considered at upstream level with the warehouses having same or different constant demands.

Furthermore, some EOQ models assumed that the quantity of product in the warehouse(s) is large

Table 1: Summary of the literature reviewed

Paper	Two-warehouse	Backlogging Type	Demand Type	Nature of the item	Trade Credit
Mahato and Mahata (2021)			Time varying	Maximum lifetime	Two – level
Mukunda et al. (2022)				Maximum lifetime	
Haruna Aliyu and Adamu (2025)	✓		Constant	Maximum lifetime	Upstream
Liang and Zhou (2011)	✓		Constant	Instantly Deteriorating	Two – level
Aliyu and Sani (2021)	✓		Constant	Instantly Deteriorating	Two – level
Aliyu (2025)	✓		Constant	Instantly Deteriorating	Upstream
Malumfashi et al. (2023)			Time varying	Deteriorating	Downstream
Chakraborty et al. (2018)		Partial backlogging	Ramp – type	Deteriorating	Upstream

enough to satisfy demand during the replenishment cycle. However, there exist situation when demand exceeds supply. This leads to shortages. Shortages are situations where a business runs out of stock. Once that happens, then it is either the sales are lost completely, partially backlogged or fully backlogged. Some researchers such as Chakraborty et al. (2018) considered shortages that are partially backlogged in developing two-warehouse inventory model. The demand is ramp-type, and the deterioration rate follows three – parameter Weibull distribution. Nath and Sen (2021) considered full backlogging when developing the two-warehouse inventory model. The item is non-instantaneously deteriorating and the demand is selling price dependent. Kumar et al. (2022) considered fixed shelf-life dependent demand in developing the inventory model in a capacity constrained environment. Shortages are allowed and partially backlogged. Shaikh et al. (2019) considered a price discount facility to customers when the demand is stock dependent, and the item is instantly deteriorating. Shortages are also allowed and partially backlogged. Khan et al (2020) developed two separate models with one that excludes shortages, and the other one includes shortages but partially backlogged under the assumption of time and an advertisement frequency dependent demand and influenced linear holding cost.

The papers reviewed are summarized as follows:

Nath and Sen (2021)	✓	Complete backlogging	Selling price dependent	Non-instantaneously deteriorating	
Kumar et al. (2022)	✓	Partial backlogging	Fixed Shelf-life dependent		
Shaikh et al. (2019)		Partial backlogging	Stock dependent	Instantly deteriorating	
Khan et al (2020)		Partial backlogging	Time and advertisement dependent		
Present paper	✓	Full backlogging	Exponential	Instantly deteriorating	Two – level

From the reviewed works in the literature, we found it motivating to integrate exponential demand that caused shortages that are fully backlogged, trade credit at both upstream and downstream level. Therefore, in this study, a two-warehouse inventory model for deteriorating items with exponential demand rate under trade credit and full backlogging has been considered and developed.

Section 2 presents the notations and assumptions of the model whereas in 3, the model formulation was given. In section 4, the optimality/convexity of the cost functions was established and in section 5, numerical illustration of the model was given. Section 5 concludes the work and recommendation for future research was also given.

1. Notations and Assumptions

The following are the notations used in developing the model:

$Q_o(t), Q_r(t)$ – the inventory levels of the own warehouse (*OW*) and rented warehouse (*RW*) at time t respectively.

W, S - stocking capacity of *OW* and the total order quantity respectively.

$D(t) = ae^{bt}$ – the exponential demand rate.

t_1, t_2, T – the time at which inventory in *OW* and in *RW* drops to zero respectively.

$\alpha(t), \beta(t)$ – the deterioration rates in *RW* and *OW* respectively.

h_o, h_r – the holding cost per unit item per unit time at *OW* and *RW* respectively.

A, δ - ordering cost per order and rate of backlogging respectively.

c, p - purchasing cost per unit item and selling price of the item respectively.

M, N – the trade credit periods offered to retailer by supplier and by retailer to customers respectively.

I_e, I_p – interest earned and the interest payable return rates by the retailer respectively.

TC – the total relevant costs per year.

The following are assumptions made in developing the mathematical model:

- i. The model considers single item.
- ii. The demand rate is exponential, $D(t) = ae^{bt}, a > 0, b > 0$
- iii. The lead time is zero and shortages are allowed.
- iv. The *OW* has limited capacity and *RW* has unlimited capacity.
- v. Trade credit is considered at upstream and downstream with $M > N$.
- vi. The dispatching policy is last in first out due to economic reasons
- vii. The shortages are fully backlogged because of the quality, good price of the item as well as the location.

3. Model Formulation

Figure 1: Pictorial representation of the model

As shown in Fig 1, at the beginning of the cycle, both warehouses are stocked with OW first and the excess going to RW . Due to economic reasons, goods in RW are first sold. At $t = t_1$ the inventory at RW drops to zero due to demand and deterioration during the period $[0, t_1]$, while goods in OW during that same period are depleted due to deterioration only. At $t = t_2$, both warehouses become empty due to depletion in OW by demand and deterioration during the period $[t_1, t_2]$. At t_2 , shortages occur because of running demand and the inventory has finished at t_2 and all customers that experience shortages are willing to wait till next arrival of goods.

The change in inventory levels in both warehouses are described by the following differential equations.

$$\frac{dQ_r(t)}{dt} = -ae^{bt} - \alpha Q_r(t) \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dQ_o(t)}{dt} = -\beta Q_o(t) \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dQ_o(t)}{dt} = -ae^{bt} - \beta Q_o(t) \quad t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dQ_o(t)}{dt} = -\delta ae^{bt} \quad t_2 \leq t \leq T \quad (4)$$

with initial and boundary conditions $Q_r(t_1) = 0$, $Q_o(0) = W$, $Q_o(t_2) = 0$ for equations (1), (2) and (3) respectively. Their respective solution is given as

$$Q_r(t) = \frac{a}{\alpha+b} (e^{bt+\alpha(t_1-t)} - e^{bt}) \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \quad (5)$$

$$Q_o(t) = we^{-\beta t} \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \quad (6)$$

$$Q_o(t) = \frac{a}{b+\beta} (e^{bt_2+\beta(t_2-t)} - e^{bt}) \quad t_1 < t < t_2 \quad (7)$$

$$Q_s(t) = \frac{a}{b} (e^{bt_2} - e^{bT}) \quad t_2 < t < T \quad (8)$$

Establishing continuity in OW at $t = t_1$, using equations (6) and (7), we see that

$$t_2 = \frac{1}{b+\beta} \left(\ln \left(\frac{b+\beta}{\alpha} W + e^{(b+\beta)t_1} \right) \right) \quad (9)$$

To get the total relevant cost we obtain the following inventory quantities

a) Ordering Cost, (OC)

The ordering cost per order is given as $OC = A$ (10)

b) Holding Cost, (HC)

The total holding cost of the warehouses during the interval $[0, t_2]$, using (5), (6) and (7), we have

$$HC = h_r \int_0^{t_1} Q_r(t) dt + h_o \int_0^{t_2} Q_o(t) dt = \frac{h_r a}{(\alpha+b)} \left[\left(be^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) + \alpha (1 - e^{-bt_1}) \right) \right] +$$

$$h_o \left[\frac{w}{\beta} (1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) + \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(b e^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) + \beta (e^{\beta t_1} - e^{\beta t_2}) \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

c) Deterioration cost (DC)

Deterioration cost in both RW and OW during the interval $[0, t_2]$, using equations (5), (6) and (7), are

$$DC = \frac{\alpha c}{(\alpha+b)} \left[\left(b e^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) + \alpha (1 - e^{\beta t_1}) \right) \right] + c \beta \left[\frac{w}{\beta} (1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) + \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(b e^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) + \beta (e^{\beta t_1} - e^{\beta t_2}) \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

d) Shortage cost (SC)

The shortage cost is given as

$$SC = \int_{t_2}^T Q_s(t) dt = \frac{a}{b^2} e^{bT} (e^{bT} - e^{bt_2}) \quad (13)$$

e) Interest earned and Interest payable by the retailer

Figure 2: Pictorial representation for the likely positions of M and N .

To get the Interest earned and paid by retailer, there are three possible cases that arises from positions of N, M, t_1 and t_2 as can be seen in Fig 2 and they are:

Case 1: $N < M \leq t_1$ (Trade credit period expired before the goods in RW finishes)

Since there are still goods in RW and OW after the expiry of the credit period M . Then, the retailer would pay interest on unsold items which, using equations (5), (6) and (7), is given as

$$I_{P1} = cI_p \left(\int_M^{t_1} Q_r(t) dt + \int_M^{t_2} Q_o(t) dt \right) = \frac{a c I_p}{\alpha + b} \left(\frac{-e^{-(\alpha+b)t_1}}{\alpha} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\alpha M}) - \frac{1}{t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{bM}) - \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{w}{\beta} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta M}) + \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(\frac{-e^{-(b+\beta)t_2}}{\beta} (e^{-\beta t_2} - e^{-\beta t_1}) - \frac{1}{b} (e^{b t_1} - e^{b t_2}) \right) \right) \quad (14)$$

Also, the retailer has sold items before M , and earned interest during $[N, M]$ and is given by

$$I_{E1} = pI_e \int_N^M D(t) dt = \frac{a p I_e}{b} (e^{bM} - e^{bN}) \quad (15)$$

Case 2: $t_1 < M \leq t_2$ (Trade credit period exceeds period when goods in RW finishes before those in OW finishes)

The retailer must pay interest for the unsold item after the time M , using (6) and (7), is given by

$$I_{P2} = cI_p \int_M^{t_2} Q_o(t) dt = \frac{a c I_p}{b+\beta} \left(\frac{e^{-(b+\beta)t_2}}{\beta} (e^{-\beta M} - e^{-\beta t_2}) - \frac{1}{b} (e^{b t_2} - e^{b M}) \right) \quad (16)$$

Retailer has generated sales revenue during $[N, M]$ and earned interest on the sale revenue generated which is

$$I_{E2} = pI_e \int_N^M D(t) dt = \frac{a p I_e}{b} (e^{bM} - e^{bN}) \quad (17)$$

Case 3: $M > t_2$ (when trade credit period of the retailer exceeds the time when goods in OW finishes)

The items have finished before the time M , therefore there is no interest payable.

$$I_{P3} = 0 \quad (18)$$

The retailer has sold all items and earned interest on the sales revenue given by

$$I_{E2} = pI_e \left(\int_N^{t_2} D(t - N) dt + D t_2 (M - t_2) \right) = pI_e \left(\frac{a}{b} \left(e^{b t_2} (t_2 - N) - \frac{1}{b} (e^{b t_2} - e^{b N}) \right) + a e^{b t_2} (M - t_2) \right) \quad (19)$$

Thus, the total relevant cost per year for the retailer is given by

$$TC_i = OC + HC + DC + SC + I_{Pi} - I_{Ei} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3$$

Hence,

Using equation (10), (11), (12), (13), (14) and (15) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
TC_1 = & \frac{1}{T} \left[A + \frac{h_r a}{(\alpha+b)} \left[\left(be^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) + \alpha(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right) \right] + h_o \left[\frac{W}{\beta} (1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(be^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) + \beta(e^{\beta t_1} - e^{\beta t_2}) \right) \right] + c \left(\frac{\alpha a}{(\alpha+b)} \left[\left(be^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) + \alpha(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right) \right] + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{a\beta}{b+\beta} \left[\left(be^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) + \beta(e^{\beta t_1} - e^{\beta t_2}) \right) \right] + \frac{1}{\beta} W(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right] \right) + \\
& \frac{a}{b} e^{bT} \left(\frac{e^{bT}}{b} - \frac{e^{bt_2}}{b} \right) + CI_p \frac{a}{\alpha+b} \left(\frac{-e^{(\alpha+b)t_1}}{\alpha} (e^{-bt_1} - e^{-\alpha M}) - \frac{1}{t_2} (e^{-bt_1} - e^{bM}) - \frac{W}{\beta} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta M}) + \right. \\
& \left. \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(\frac{-e^{(b+\beta)t_2}}{\beta} (e^{-\beta t_2} - e^{-\beta t_1}) - \frac{1}{b} (e^{bt_1} - e^{bt_2}) \right) - \frac{aPI_e}{b} (e^{bM} - e^{bN}) \right] \quad (20)
\end{aligned}$$

Using equation (10), (11), (12), (13), (16) and (17) we find that

$$\begin{aligned}
TC_2 = & \frac{1}{T} \left[A + \frac{h_r a}{(\alpha+b)} \left[\left(be^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) + \alpha(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right) \right] + h_o \left[\frac{W}{\beta} (1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(be^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) + \beta(e^{\beta t_1} - e^{\beta t_2}) \right) \right] + c \left(\frac{\alpha a}{(\alpha+b)} \left[\left(be^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) + \alpha(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right) \right] + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{a\beta}{b+\beta} \left[\left(be^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) + \beta(e^{\beta t_1} - e^{\beta t_2}) \right) \right] + \frac{1}{\beta} W(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right] \right) + \\
& \frac{a}{b} e^{bT} \left(\frac{e^{bT}}{b} - \frac{e^{bt_2}}{b} \right) + CI_p \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(\frac{e^{(b+\beta)t_2}}{\beta} (e^{-\beta M} - e^{-\beta t_2}) - \frac{1}{b} (e^{bt_2} - e^{bM}) \right) - PI_e \frac{a}{b} (e^{bM} - e^{bN}) \right] \quad (21)
\end{aligned}$$

And

Using equation (10), (11), (12), (13), (18) and (19) we see that

$$\begin{aligned}
TC_3 = & \frac{1}{T} \left[A + \frac{h_r a}{(\alpha+b)} \left[\left(be^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) + \alpha(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right) \right] + h_o \left[\frac{W}{\beta} (1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(be^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) + \beta(e^{\beta t_1} - e^{\beta t_2}) \right) \right] + c \left(\frac{\alpha a}{(\alpha+b)} \left[\left(be^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) + \alpha(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right) \right] + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{a\beta}{b+\beta} \left[\left(be^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) + \beta(e^{\beta t_1} - e^{\beta t_2}) \right) \right] + \frac{1}{\beta} W(1 - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right] \right) - \\
& PI_e \left(\frac{a}{b} \left(e^{bt_2} (t_2 - N) - \frac{1}{b} (e^{bt_2} + e^{bN}) \right) + ae^{bt_2} (M - t_2) \right) \quad (22)
\end{aligned}$$

2. Optimality Conditions

The necessary conditions for TC_1 to have minimum are $\frac{\partial TC_1}{\partial t_1} = 0$, $\frac{\partial TC_1}{\partial t_2} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial TC_1}{\partial T} = 0$.

Using equation (20), differentiating with respect to t_1, t_2 and T and setting the result to zero, we respectively have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{T} \left[h_r \left(abe^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) \right) + h_o \left[We^{-\beta t_1} + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(-\beta be^{(b+\beta)t_2 - \beta t_1} - \beta^2 e^{\beta t_1} \right) \right] + \right. \\
& \left. c \left[\left(\alpha abe^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1}) \right) \right] - \right. \\
& \left. \frac{a\beta}{b+\beta} \left(\beta be^{(b+\beta)t_2 - \beta t_1} + \beta^2 e^{\beta t_1} \right) + We^{-\beta t_1} \right) + \\
& CI_p \frac{a}{\alpha+b} \left(\frac{-(\alpha+b)}{\alpha} e^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (e^{-bt_1} - e^{-\alpha M}) - \frac{b}{\alpha} e^{-bt_1} + \right. \\
& \left. \frac{b}{t_2} e^{-bt_1} + We^{-\beta t_1} - \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(e^{(b+\beta)t_2 - \beta t_1} + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{1}{b} e^{-bt_1} \right) \right] = 0 \quad (23)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{T} \left[h_o \left(\frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(b(b+\beta) e^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) \right) + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. b\beta e^{bt_2} - \beta^2 e^{\beta t_2} \right) + c \left[\frac{a\beta}{(b+\beta)} \left(b(b+\beta) e^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2}) \right) + b\beta e^{bt_2} - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \beta^2 e^{\beta t_2} \right] - \frac{a}{b} e^{b(T-t_2)} + CI_p \frac{a}{\alpha+b} \left(\frac{1}{t_2^2} (e^{-bt_1} - e^{bM}) + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(\frac{-(b+\beta)e^{(b+\beta)t_2}}{\beta} (e^{-\beta t_2} - e^{-\beta t_1}) \right) \right) \right] = 0 \quad (24)
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\frac{1}{T} \left[ae^{bT} \left(\frac{e^{bT}}{b} - \frac{e^{bt_2}}{b} \right) - \frac{a}{b} e^{b^2 T} - TC_1 \right] = 0 \quad (25)$$

Solving equations (23), (24) and (25) simultaneously give the critical values of t_1, t_2 and T . To characterize the critical point, it is enough to show that the sufficient conditions are satisfied. To achieve this, we show that the determinant of the Hessian matrix

$$\begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_2 \partial t_1} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial T \partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_1 \partial t_2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_2^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial T \partial t_2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_1 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_2 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial T^2} \end{vmatrix}_{(t_1^*, t_2^*, T^*)}$$

is positive definite at (t_1^*, t_2^*, T^*) , which holds.

The necessary conditions for a minimum of TC_2 are $\frac{\partial TC_2}{\partial t_1} = 0$, $\frac{\partial TC_2}{\partial t_2} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial TC_2}{\partial T} = 0$.

Using equation (21), differentiating with respect to t_1, t_2 and T , setting the derivative to zero, and respectively get

$$\frac{1}{T} \left[h_r (abe^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1})) + h_o [We^{-\beta t_1} + \frac{a}{b+\beta} (-\beta be^{(b+\beta)t_2 - \beta t_1} - \beta^2 e^{\beta t_1})] + c \left([(\alpha abe^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1})) - \frac{a\beta}{b+\beta} (\beta be^{(b+\beta)t_2 - \beta t_1} + \beta^2 e^{\beta t_1}) + We^{-\beta t_1}] \right) \right] = 0 \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{1}{T} \left[h_o \left(\frac{a}{b+\beta} (b(b+\beta)e^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2})) + b\beta e^{bt_2} - \beta^2 e^{\beta t_2} \right) + c \left[\frac{a\beta}{(b+\beta)} (b(b+\beta)e^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2})) + b\beta e^{bt_2} - \beta^2 e^{\beta t_2} \right] - \frac{a}{b} e^{b(T+t_2)} + CI_P \frac{a}{b+\beta} \left(\frac{(b+\beta)e^{(b+\beta)t_2}}{\beta} (e^{-\beta M} - e^{-\beta t_2}) \right) \right] = 0 \quad (27)$$

And

$$\frac{1}{T} \left[ae^{bT} \left(\frac{e^{bT}}{b} - \frac{e^{bt_2}}{b} \right) - \frac{a}{b} e^{2bT} - TC_2 \right] = 0 \quad (28)$$

Solving equations (26), (27) and (28) simultaneously give the critical values of t_1, t_2 and T . To show the minima exist and unique, it is enough to establish that the determinant of the Hessian matrix

$$\begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial t_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial t_2 \partial t_1} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial T \partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial t_1 \partial t_2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial t_2^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial T \partial t_2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial t_1 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial t_2 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_2}{\partial T^2} \end{vmatrix}_{(t_1^*, t_2^*, T^*)} \quad \text{is positive definite at } (t_1^*, t_2^*, T^*), \text{ which is true.}$$

The necessary conditions for a minimum of TC_3 are $\frac{\partial TC_3}{\partial t_1} = 0$, $\frac{\partial TC_3}{\partial t_2} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial TC_3}{\partial T} = 0$.

Differentiating equation (22) with respect to t_1, t_2 and T and setting the result to zero, we respectively see that

$$\frac{1}{T} \left[h_r (abe^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1})) + h_o [We^{-\beta t_1} + \frac{a}{b+\beta} (-\beta be^{(b+\beta)t_2 - \beta t_1} - \beta^2 e^{\beta t_1})] +$$

$$c \left([(\alpha abe^{(\alpha+b)t_1} (1 - e^{-\alpha t_1})) - \frac{a\beta}{b+\beta} (\beta be^{(b+\beta)t_2 - \beta t_1} + \beta^2 e^{\beta t_1}) + We^{-\beta t_1}] \right) = 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{1}{T} \left[h_o \left(\frac{a}{b+\beta} (b(b+\beta)e^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2})) + be^{bt_2} - \beta^2 e^{\beta t_2} \right) + c \left[\frac{a\beta}{(b+\beta)} (b(b+\beta)e^{(b+\beta)t_2} (e^{-\beta t_1} - e^{-\beta t_2})) + be^{bt_2} - \beta^2 e^{\beta t_2} \right] - \frac{P_1 e^a}{Tb} \left(\frac{e^{bt_2}}{b} (t_2 - N) + e^{bt_2} - \frac{e^{bt_2}}{b^2} \right) + ae^{bt} ((M - t_2) - t_2) \right] = 0 \quad (30)$$

and

$$\frac{1}{T} [TC_3] = 0 \quad (31)$$

Solving equations (29), (30) and (31) simultaneously give the values of t_1, t_2 and T .

For sufficient condition, we show that the determinant of the Hessian matrix

$$\begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial t_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial t_2 \partial t_1} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial T \partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial t_1 \partial t_2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial t_2^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial T \partial t_2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial t_1 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial t_2 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_3}{\partial T^2} \end{vmatrix}_{(t_1^*, t_2^*, T^*)} \quad \text{is positive definite,}$$

which holds.

3. Numerical Examples

To validate the model, a numerical example is given which was solved using Newton – Raphson method and implemented using PHYTON programming. The algorithm for the Newton-Raphson is:

Step 1: Start with $k = 0$ and the initial value of $X_0 = (t_{10}, t_{20}, T_0)$

Step 2: By using (27), (28) and (29), find the initial $X_0 = (t_{10}, t_{20}, T_0)$

Step 3: Use the result in step 2 to determine the

optimal $X_{k+1} = (t_1^*, t_2^*, T^*)$ by using the Newton-Raphson formula

$$X_{k+1} = X_k - (H_f|_{X_k})^{-1} \nabla f|_{X_k} \quad \text{where } H_f|_{X_k} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_2 \partial t_1} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial T \partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_1 \partial t_2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_2^2} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial T \partial t_2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_1 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial t_2 \partial T} & \frac{\partial^2 TC_1}{\partial T^2} \end{pmatrix} |_{X_k} \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla f|_{X_k} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial TC_1}{\partial t_1} \\ \frac{\partial TC_1}{\partial t_2} \\ \frac{\partial TC_1}{\partial T} \end{pmatrix} |_{X_k} \quad \text{for } K = 1, 2, 3 \dots$$

Step 4: If the difference between X_{k+1} and X_k is sufficiently small, i.e. (ie $|X_{k+1} - X_k| < 0.0001$), then

X_{k+1} is the optimal (t_1^*, t_2^*, T^*), stop. Otherwise set $X_{k+1} = X_k$ and go back to step 3.

Example 1: for case 1 ($N < M \leq t_1$)

Table 2: Result of the Numerical Example

Cases	t_1	t_2	T	TC
Case 1 (Example 1)	0.109506	0.270386	0.768021	17753.294152
Case 2 (Example 2)	0.092424	1.336342	2.483865	25974.045789
Case 3 (Example 3)	1.701702	2.786877	2.836163	125454.990056

Sensitivity analysis for testing the importance of parameters was carried out and the results are given in the tables below:

Consider an inventory system with the following input parameters as obtained in (Aliyu and Sani ,2022) : $A = 500$; $w = 2500$; $h_r = 3$; $h_0 = 1$; $a = 14$; $b = 2$; $\alpha = .002$; $\beta = 0.1$; $M = 0.12$ (44 days); $N = 0.08$ (29 days); $c = 50$; $p = 55$; $I_p = 0.13$; $I_e = 0.08$.

Example 2: for case 2 ($t_1 < M \leq t_2$)

The Parameters and their values are the same as in Example 1 except for $M = 0.56$ (204 Days) and $N = 0.12$ (44 Days).

Example 3: for case 3 ($t_2 < M$)

The Parameters and their values are the same as in example 1 except for $M = 0.13$ (48 Days) and $N = 0.12$ (44 Days).

The results are presented in table 2 below:

Table 3: Sensitivity analysis result for Case 1

Parameters	%Change in Parameters	New t_1	%Change in t_1	New t_2	%Change in t_2	New T	%Change in T	New TC_1	%Change in TC_1
A	-50%	0.730427	5.670201	0.987367	2.651694	2.712768	2.532153	11454.992368	-0.3547681
	-25%	0.730427	5.670201	0.987368	2.651698	2.712768	2.532153	11454.982227	-0.3547686
	0%	0.109506	0.000000	0.270386	0.000000	0.768021	0.000000	17753.294152	0.000000
	25%	0.730427	5.670201	0.987366	2.651691	2.712767	2.532152	11454.961942	-0.354770
	50%	0.730427	5.670201	0.987366	2.651691	2.712767	2.532152	11454.951790	-0.354770
M	-50%	0.963174	7.795628	0.096442	-0.643316	0.9659027	0.257651	314616.315780	16.721574
	-25%	0.730411	5.670055	0.988377	2.655428	2.7149963	2.535055	11529.402903	-0.3505767
	0%	0.109506	0.000000	0.270386	0.000000	0.9659028	0.257652	17753.294152	0.000000
	25%	0.730049	5.666749	1.010729	2.738097	2.764041	2.598913	13299.065631	-0.2508959
	50%	0.729667	5.663260	1.033381	2.821873	2.813025	2.662693	15347.713559	-0.1355005
W	-50%	0.109148	-0.003269	0.314893	0.164605	0.768149	0.000167	17607.459961	-0.0082145
	-25%	0.103865	-0.051513	0.714804	1.643643	0.766636	-0.001803	16072.919197	-0.0946514
	0%	0.109506	0.000000	0.270386	0.000000	0.768021	0.000000	17753.294152	0.000000
	25%	0.730486	5.670740	0.987377	2.651731	2.712809	2.532207	11456.166627	-0.3547019
	50%	0.10656	-0.026903	0.488483	0.806614	0.767228	-0.001033	16720.499363	-0.0581748
h_r	-50%	0.092423	-0.156001	1.336341	3.942345	2.483865	2.234111	25974.045789	0.463055
	-25%	0.7304271	5.670202	0.987367	2.651694	2.712768	2.532153	11454.972183	-0.3547692
	0%	0.109506	0.000000	0.270386	0.000000	0.768021	0.000000	17753.294152	0.000000
	25%	0.7304271	5.670202	0.987367	2.651694	2.712768	2.532153	11454.971984	-0.3547692
	50%	0.7304271	5.670202	0.987367	2.651694	2.712767	2.532152	11454.971984	-0.3547692
h_0	-50%	0.727633	5.644686	0.987328	2.651550	2.710676	2.529430	11406.260219	-0.357513
	-25%	0.729032	5.657462	0.987348	2.651624	2.711723	2.530793	11430.626732	-0.3561405
	0%	0.109506	0.000000	0.270386	0.000000	0.768021	0.000000	17753.294152	0.000000
	25%	0.731819	5.682912	0.987386	2.651765	2.713809	2.533509	11479.296289	-0.3533991
	50%	0.733208	5.695597	0.987404	2.651831	2.714848	2.534862	11503.599357	-0.352030

Table 4: Sensitivity analysis result for Case 2

Parameters	%Change in Parameter s	New t_1	%Change in t_1	New t_2	%Change in t_2	New T	%Change in T	New TC_2	%Change in TC_2
	-50%	0.001078	-0.988334	1.3545664	0.013637	2.446614	-0.014997	25499.976875	-0.018252
	-25%	0.098751	0.068458	1.3082144	-0.021048	2.481578	-0.000921	25653.523969	-0.012340
A	0%	0.092424	0.000000	1.336342	0.000000	2.483865	0.000000	25974.045789	0.000000
	25%	0.037827	-0.590724	13.200339	8.877964	2.440339	-0.017523	28887.366206	0.112163
	50%	0.027273	-0.704915	1.4129547	0.057330	2.450035	-0.013620	26419.552666	0.017152
	-50%	1.857593	19.098602	1.3778254	0.031043	1.913863	-0.229482	80299.395122	2.091524
	-25%	1.856826	19.090301	1.5053469	0.126468	1.913802	-0.229506	79919.518451	2.076899
M	0%	0.092424	0.000000	1.336342	0.000000	2.483865	0.000000	25974.045789	0.000000
	25%	4.469775	47.36163	4.5264421	2.387188	2.147113	-0.135576	13719.956566	-0.471782
	50%	0.327873	2.547493	1.4414854	0.078680	2.402425	-0.032788	32805.111113	0.262996
	-50%	0.068513	-0.258708	1.9646047	0.470136	2.448513	-0.014233	25917.117981	-0.002192
	-25%	0.122166	0.321797	5.6927985	3.259986	2.451473	-0.013041	32868.609050	0.265440
W	0%	0.092424	0.000000	1.336342	0.000000	2.483865	0.000000	25974.045789	0.000000
	25%	0.064363	-0.303608	12.885554	8.642407	2.447199	-0.014762	25941.745178	-0.001244
	50%	0.133942	0.449211	21.661686	15.209687	2.446432	-0.015070	23401.855162	-0.099029
	-50%	0.034017	-0.631948	1.3628955	0.019870	2.445989	-0.015249	26553.924303	0.022325
	-25%	0.104030	0.125570	1.3020849	-0.025635	2.481766	-0.000845	25518.803539	-0.017527
h_r	0%	0.092424	0.000000	1.336342	0.000000	2.483865	0.000000	25974.045789	0.000000
	25%	0.024392	-0.736083	12.898701	8.652245	2.428678	-0.022218	25631.226009	-0.013199
	50%	0.037296	-0.596465	13.58295	9.164277	2.444860	-0.015703	26672.397878	0.026887
	-50%	0.023663	-0.743976	55.006889	40.162284	2.436975	-0.018878	28068.131199	0.080622
	-25%	0.113688	0.230070	51.662873	37.659918	2.473501	-0.004172	34735.550570	0.337318
h_0	0%	0.092424	0.000000	1.336342	0.000000	2.483865	0.000000	25974.045789	0.000000
	25%	1.856367	19.085334	1.733233	0.296998	1.913574	-0.229598	79706.441375	2.068696
	50%	1.856408	19.085777	1.730340	0.294833	1.913544	-0.229610	80270.031544	2.090394

Table 5: Sensitivity analysis result for Case 3

Parameters	%Change in Parameter s	New t_1	%Change in t_1	New t_2	%Change in t_2	New T	%Change in T	New TC_3	%Change in TC_3
A	-50%	1.7017023	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
	-25%	1.7017023	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
	0%	1.7017023	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
	25%	1.7017023	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
	50%	1.7017023	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
M	-50%	5.9622182	2.503679	5.167198	0.854118	9.026462	2.182632	7.14286924456	-0.999943
	-25%	4.229595	1.485509	12.4585112	3.470420	3.634729	0.281566	121414.408959	-0.032207
	0%	1.701702	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
	25%	5.971954	2.509401	5.17449101	0.856735	5.345150	0.884641	1.22474368924	-0.999990
	50%	4.2591411	1.502871	2.151720	-0.22791	8.646730	2.048742	53186.8259242	-0.576049
W	-50%	5.730460	2.367488	5.008796	0.797279	5.0459214	0.779137	9.22466484835	-0.999926
	-25%	1.7324328	0.018059	2.791581	0.001688	2.8373116	0.000405	127260.676875	0.014393
	0%	1.701702	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
	25%	4.8207883	1.832922	2.312555	-0.170198	2.492587	-0.121141	213174.367945	0.699210
	50%	1.3575308	-0.202251	3.700094	0.327685	14.62744	4.157475	12674.1115162	-0.898975
h_r	-50%	5.725482	2.364562	4.96015198	0.779825	4.5117886	0.590807	9.18024594434	-0.999927
	-25%	5.7280011	2.366042	4.985001	0.788741	7.5893592	1.675925	5.79287506901	-0.999954
	0%	1.701702	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
	25%	5.7328759	2.368907	5.031751	0.805516	3.110809	0.096837	1.58098967456	-0.999987
	50%	1.580990	-0.070936	2.411366	-0.134742	2.1383379	-0.246046	228092.008282	0.818118
h_o	-50%	4.1567857	1.442722	3.065723	0.100057	4.9013929	0.728177	154622.328053	0.232492
	-25%	154622.33	90862.34	15.176424	4.445674	36.764416	11.96273	1608.34564994	-0.987180
	0%	1.701702	0.000000	2.786877	0.000000	2.836163	0.000000	125454.990056	0.000000
	25%	4.2742675	1.511760	2.70032598	-0.031057	3.7366918	0.317517	151328.517935	0.206238
	50%	2.3049273	0.354484	1.951621	-0.29971	1.8684517	-0.341204	148877.299570	0.186699

4.2 Discussion of the Results

It is observed from Tables 3, 4 and 5 that:

- As the ordering cost A increases t_1, t_2, T and TC also increase for 1 and 3 cases. In practical sense, when the ordering cost is high, the retailer tends to order more goods to reduce frequent orders that leads to an increase in the overall total Cost of the model.
- As the ordering cost A decreases t_1, t_2, T and TC remind the same for 1 and 3 cases. In practical sense, when the ordering cost is less, the retailer tends to order goods any time they pleased which in turn make the overall total cost to be the same
- As the trade credit period M increases, t_2, T and TC increases. This aligns with real-life expectations, as trade credit period increase demand rate typically increase the optimal replenishment length increases. In practical situations, when the trade credit period increase, retailers tend to order more goods, which results in more sales and reduces in total cost.
- As the OW capacity increases, T and TC increase for all cases. In real-life situations, if the capacity of OW increases, the replenishment length increases due increase in goods. This increases in replenishment length, in turn, leads to a decrease in the total cost.
- As the holding cost of RW h_r increases, t_1, t_2, T and TC *also increase for all cases. This aligns with expectations in real life. When the total holding cost is high and the annual total relevant inventory costs increase, retailers tend to sell fewer items as customers tend to buy from cheaper retailers. Consequently, the time it takes for the inventory to reach zero also increases.
- As the holding cost of OW h_o increases, t_1, t_2, T and TC *also increase for all cases. This aligns with expectations in real life. When these Total Holding cost is high and the annual total

relevant inventory costs increase, retailers tend to sell fewer items as customers tend to buy from cheaper retailers.

7. As the upstream credit period M increases, t_1 , t_2 , T and TC is unstable (the trend cannot be determined) for all cases.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study has successfully integrated capacity constrained warehouse, trade credit, exponential demand, and shortage that is fully backlogged because of many factors such as proximity, genuine price, quality of the items. From the result of the model, it was found out that the holding cost, warehouse capacity and the upstream trade credit rate significantly influence the determination of the optimal cycle period for replenishment and the maximum total profit.

Since the model considers shortages that are fully backlogged, exponential demand and trade credit, therefore, for it to be more realizable, partial backlogging can be considered as against full backlogging because of its more practicability in real life. Also, majority of goods obtainable in the market do not obey the exponential demand, therefore, linear demand can be considered. Despite its roles in stimulating demand, trade credit brings the issues of credit riskiness. Therefore, a discount can be introduced to the model for large orders or partial trade credit. There exist some items that maintain their quality before they start to deteriorate, therefore non-instantaneous deteriorating item can be considered as against instantaneous deteriorating item considered in the model.

Data Availability Statement

Not applicable as no data was used for this research.

Disclosure of Interest

There is no competing interest.

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